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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF LEVEL OF MEDIATIONS ON PAIN AND
SATISFACTION LEVEL OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING
ABDOMINAL SURGERY**

Muazzma Siddiqa, Faraz Saeed, Hasnain Afzal

Article Received: November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

The main objective of the study was to analyse the level of mediations on pain and satisfaction level of patients undergoing abdominal surgery. This cross sectional study was conducted at Health deptment Punjab. The study was performed with 124 patients undergoing abdominal surgery under general anesthesia aged 18-65, with no diagnosis of cancer, no chronic pain, hospitalized for at least 24 hour following the surgical procedure, undergoing elective surgery and agreeing to participate. The data was collected from 124 patients with mean age 18 to 40 years. The data was collected from both genders. Of a total of 124 abdominal-surgery patient subjects, 58.1% were male, 94.3% were married, 61.3% had undergone surgery, and 41.1% had undergone total gastrectomy. Among the 124 participants, 47 were included in the control group, 36 in experimental group. Regarding their general characteristics, no significant differences in any aspects were observed. It is concluded that preoperative nursing intervention for pain has positive effects for patients undergoing abdominal surgery.

Corresponding author:

Muazzma Siddiqa,

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INTRODUCTION:

Post-operative care is the process of providing care to patient after surgery. Post-operative care is necessary to reduce the occurrence of complications like shock, hemorrhage, pneumonia, respiratory depression, deep vein thrombosis, urinary tract infection, pressure sores, incisional hernia, bowel obstruction, infection and to enhance recovery of the surgical wound, and bring back patient to normal level of health and functioning¹⁻². Post-operative care must be provided to patient for immediate recovery and prognosis of the patient after surgery. Post operative nursing care include ,providing interventions such as continuous observation and monitoring of vital signs, maintenance of personal hygiene , early ambulation ,steam inhalation, care of surgical wound and incentive spirometry³. Post-operative care is an essential aspect in post-operative period as it provides opportunities for nurses to care for patients in a comprehensive and holistic manner so as to achieve early recovery of patient health status⁴⁻⁵.

Anxiety is an individual experience and it is a concept that is difficult to describe with words. No matter how major or minor an operation is, it tends to raise a certain level of anxiety in every patient. Hospitalization for surgical procedure can be experienced as a threat or stressor and may produce anxiety in patients⁶.

Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study was to analyse the level of mediations on pain and satisfaction level of patients undergoing abdominal surgery.

Table 01: Differences in patients Knowledge regarding Pain Management

Variable	Pre	Post		F	p
		2 weeks	4 week		
	<i>M ± SD</i>	<i>M ± SD</i>	<i>M ± SD</i>		
Pain management	31.96 ± 3.62	32.50 ± 3.50	37.93 ± 2.36***	14.46	<.001

*** $p < .001$.

DISCUSSION:

Despite progress in reducing pain, a universal experience, individuals still report experiencing it at various levels. For most patients, admission to hospital for surgery can be very stressful. Studies in this area support that requirements of patients to be informed in the preoperative period are not met, and anxiety can arise from lack of information⁷. In this study, all the patients who did not have adequate information about their disease and operation (51.7% in the study group -before they were instructed- and 45% in the control group) stated that they wished to get information from the healthcare personnel⁸. Emotional and psychological surgical

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Health deptment Punjab. The study population consisted of patients undergoing abdominal surgery (benign prostate hypertrophy, appendicitis, acute cholecystitis, inguinal hernia, acute abdomen, uterine myoma, ovarian cyst, uterine bleeding, polyp etc.) in the surgical department. The study was performed with 124 patients undergoing abdominal surgery under general anesthesia aged 18-65, with no diagnosis of cancer, no chronic pain, hospitalized for at least 24 hour following the surgical procedure, undergoing elective surgery and agreeing to participate.

The data obtained were transferred to computer for analysis using SPSS version 15.00 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) software. A p value <0.05 was considered significant. Numbers, percentages, and mean plus standard deviation were used at analysis.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 124 patients with mean age 18 to 40 years. The data was collected from both genders. Of a total of 124 abdominal-surgery patient subjects, 58.1% were male, 94.3% were married, 61.3% had undergone surgery, and 41.1% had undergone total gastrectomy. Among the 124 participants, 47 were included in the control group, 36 in experimental group. Regarding their general characteristics, no significant differences in any aspects were observed.

preparation plays an important role in many areas of nursing⁹.

The powerful social factors affecting the reactions of women after hysterectomy are indicated as the educational status, income level, cultural structure, age at hysterectomy, short decision period before the operation, little support from the spouse and existence of a mental disorder preoperatively. In our study, no relationship was found between age groups and the level of anxiety ($p > .05$)¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that preoperative nursing intervention for pain has positive effects for patients

undergoing abdominal surgery. The intervention used in this study could serve as a guide for patients to improve the pain care of these patients.

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